

LIFE SKILLS IMPORTANCE FOR SCHOOL PUPILS IN ISRAELI REALITY

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This paper points out importance of life skills' early acquisition in order to help school pupils build better lives and get far away from dangerous behaviors and addictions. Specific emotional, cognitive, and behavioral and resilience skills play a vital part in ensuring an adolescent's personal and social life. Likewise, psychosocial skills allow individuals to recognize, interact, influence, and relate to others in different environments. Children and adolescents with psychosocial skills are more likely to enjoy mental health and wellbeing. Based on these assumptions, the Israeli Ministry of Education introduced life skill education as a part of the curriculum for the school system, from early childhood through secondary school. Israeli psychological counseling unit in the Ministry of Education reasoned that additional skills, such as emotional, cognitive, behavioral and resilience development in adolescents would help them navigate through the psychologically troubling years of adolescence. The author describes Life Skills programs which were developed and introduced by Israeli Education system.

Key words: *Life Skills; Socio-Emotional Learning (SEL); Israeli Ministry of Education; Self-Regulation, Management and Outlet (ONBI) Holistic Model.*

INTRODUCTION

There is plethora of evidence that adolescents who face personal, cognitive, and social skills deficits are prone to drug and alcohol use, bullying, violence, malnutrition and other socio-economic and environmental challenges. Specific emotional, cognitive, and behavioral and resilience skills play a vital part in ensuring an adolescent's personal and social

life [2]. Likewise, psychosocial skills allow individuals to recognize, interact, influence, and relate to others in different environments. Children and adolescents with psychosocial skills are more likely to enjoy mental health and wellbeing [3]. Based on these assumptions, the Israeli Ministry of Education introduced life skill education as a part of the curriculum for the school system, from early childhood through secondary school. Israeli psychological counseling unit in the Ministry of Education reasoned those additional skills, such as emotional, cognitive, behavioral and resilience development in adolescents would help them navigate through the psychologically troubling years of adolescence [5].

SOCIO-EMOTIONAL LEARNING (SEL) PROGRAM IN ISRAELI EDUCATION SYSTEM

Kishuri Hayeem (Hebrew for life skills), has been identified by the Ministry of Education as an essential resource for developing psychosocial, emotional, cognitive, behavioral and resilience skills to negotiate every day challenges and productive involvement in the community. In an official statement by the Ministry of Education [1], the life skills program was detailed for it to become part of the curricula. Very fast, it became rather clear that there is a growing demand to educate adolescents with life skills to help them deal with their day-to-day life challenges and transition into adulthood with informed healthy choices.

The official stand of life skills program is that Life Skills is a developmental program from the first to the twelfth grade, which works to develop students' emotional and social competence, and to strengthen their ability to cope with different life situations. The program includes developmental and preventive issues. These are structured arrangements for conversations with students about their lives, their experience of their age tasks, formulation of their identities, their sexuality, their encounter with risk behaviors and the different life situations they experience [1].

Freidman [1], a member of the initiative for applied educational research committee, discussed the importance of cultivating life skills in the school system. According to her, cultivating socio-emotional learning (SEL) is considered an important and inseparable aspect of educational and learning processes, partly in response to the accelerated technological development and social and cultural changes that characterize the

21st century. Acquiring SEL should positively reflect adolescents' improved academic achievement, positive social functioning, ability to adapt to complex situations, decrease in behavioral problems and emotional distress. Furthermore, mastering these skills, suggested Freidman [1], is manifested over time in behavior shaped by internal beliefs, values, and is accompanied by "seeing" the other, as well as accepting responsibility for one's choices and behavior. In the broader context, it was found that there is a connection between these skills and successful personal, social, and occupational functioning.

Most of the SEL programs running today in Israel and worldwide were intended to build and strengthen five interconnected skill sets among students: self-awareness, self-regulation, social awareness, relationship management, and taking responsibility.

The Israeli Ministry of Education administration recognizes the importance of socio-emotional skills and handles the issue in diverse ways, with the common denominator being the perception that the school arena serves as the "training ground" for students' socio-emotional development. It is an inseparable part of their mental well-being, their cognitive development and of broadening their world of knowledge. The thinking at the Ministry of Education is that these socio-emotional competencies are acquired skills – they can be taught and trained for. Currently, in the education system, the Psychological Counseling Service (Shefi) is responsible for teaching and developing social and emotional skills and it does so on several fronts, the major one being through the Life Skills Program [5].

LIFE SKILLS PROGRAM CONTENTS

Shadmi [4], president of the Psychological Counseling Service, described Kishuri Hayeem- "Life Skills" - as a program that is based on a holistic psycho-educational worldview, which believes in the interplay between the learning process and the emotional experience. The educator (teacher, educator, counselor), who will adopt the concept of "life skills", will soon learn to diagnose every life situation in the school and in general, as an educational resource to improve life skills. "Life skills sessions" promote multidimensional reference to diverse life situations. The education that guides the "life skills" sessions accompanies its students in developing a differentiating vision within the situation, encourages

them to identify - what coping tools are available to them? In what ways do they manage themselves and / or the situation? What is effective for them? Effective for them, and in general, what unique “adaptive muscle” is strengthened by different life situations?

Regarding the contents of the program, Shadmi [4] suggested several points that should be addressed. The “Life Skills” program should address the universal developmental needs of the youth, the local school, and classroom needs at the particular time. The program should address:

- issues that engage teens according to their emotional development in age: such as Sexual Identity, Temptation and Social Stress, Sexual Harassment, Alcohol Drinking, Substance Abuse, Attention to Relevant Life Situations such as Recruiting to the Israeli defense Army (IDF), Traveling to Poland (visiting memorials for the holocaust), Volunteering, Contributing to the Society, and More.
- Providing the ability to cope with stressful situations that require regulating and managing emotions.
- Addressing value issues related to interpersonal relationships such as: strengthening acceptance and tolerance values, values and skills related to providing help, receiving help, teamwork, mutual guarantee, and more.
- Providing an answer to the adolescent’s strength as a gatekeeper - developing a position of social responsibility, sensitivity to others and their needs. The courage to take a personal stand even when, contrary to the opinion of the significant group of equals, the power to resist hurting others and bullying.
- Addressing school, local authority, and educational goals.
- Addressing topical events in the school, city, country, and around the world including various crisis events. The “Life Skills” program will provide a holistic response to coping with each life situation through skills and skills in five focus areas simultaneously: self-identity, emotional regulation, interpersonal competence, self-management, and stress and crisis risk situations [4].

SELF REGULATION, MANAGEMENT AND OUTLET (ONBI) HOLISTIC MODEL

Zimmerman, et al. [6], part of the psychological services in the Israeli

Ministry of Education, described in details the model upon which the whole program of life skills is based. The ONBI model (Hebrew initials for self, regulation, management and outlet) is a holistic concept of the Life Skills Program. The “Life Skills” lessons aim to promote a holistic view of the student about himself or herself in any life situation. Each skill is significant in itself and at the same time, reflected and reflected in the other skills. The range of life skills can be sorted into five centers. The five focal points of the “ONBI” model are:

1. The focus of self-identity: This focus is on getting to know one’s self and developing self-awareness. It’s about getting to know my body, feelings, thoughts and behavior as well as my gender identity, sexual identity, cultural identity, attitudes and values

2. Emotional regulation, focus, and self-direction: It is a person’s ability to regulate his emotions (calm anxiety, reduce anger), direct his behavior, functioning while examining options, and choosing between them. For example, the ability to recognize real-time anger feelings that can lead to aggressive and violent behaviors and regulated through internal speech, or self-soothing methods to develop more self-control and prevent violent behavior, and more

3. Self-management in daily life tasks (learning, work, and leisure): It is the ability to manage our immediate environments and perform the life tasks facing each of us (learning, working) according to the developmental stage, on the best side. Intrinsic motivation influences the formation of a sense of meaning in life and reinforces self-worth.

4. Between You - The focus of interpersonal competence in various circles: constructive communication, developing and maintaining relationships, communication with family members, with age group, with authority figures, with friends and intimate relationships

5. There is an outlet - the focus of dealing with stress, risk, and crisis. Reality invites us to cope with moderate stress situations (there are stoppages and I am late for a meeting (until severe crisis situations) loss, divorce, injuries (coping skills to identify stress sensations, event identification). As a threatening factor, identifying the automatic personal response to the event, and applying a variety of skills are taught to emotionally regulate and soothe.

The model is presented in the following figure:

Figure 1. ONBI model schematic representation [5]

“ONBI” model represents an integrative concept of internal power. The five centers are presented in a circular model that emphasizes the space that creates the whole. The synergy between the five centers over time, the simultaneous work on all five centers together, and on each focus individually, it what reinforces the presence of the components that exist in the focal point of the individual and promotes well-being and mental health. In other words, for the model to be beneficial, all five centers should be addressed, and any efficient intervention plan should address all five centers, one at a time, and together at the same time. The message to be realized from the model is that effective intervention deals with all five centers. Different focus on each center according should be stressed according to the nature of the plan.

SUMMARY

This paper points out the fact that without some basic life skills it is difficult to develop a proper level of life for modern school pupils, sin-

ce psychosocial skills allow individuals to recognize, interact, influence, and relate to others in different environments. Children and adolescents with psychosocial skills are more likely to enjoy mental health and well-being [3]. Based on these assumptions, the Israeli Ministry of Education introduced life skill education as a part of the curriculum for the school system, from early childhood through secondary school. The paper describes some Israeli programs promoting life skills for children and their main contents.

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